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СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Рўзиев Феруз Ғиёсович ГЕМОМРАГИК ИНСУЛЬТЛАР РЕАБИЛИТАЦИЯСИДА ВЕРТИКАЛИЗАЦИЯНИНГ ФАРҚЛИ ЖИҲАТЛАРИ.....	6
2. Hazratqulov Rustam Bafoyevich, Kariyev Shuhrat Maratovich, Kim Andrey Afanasyevich TRAUMATIK INTRAKRANIAL GEMATOMALARNING TURLARINI TASHHIS QO'YISH VA DIFFERENTIAL DAVOLASH ALGORITMI.....	11
3. Aliyev Mansur Abduxoliqovich, Mamadaliyev Abdurahmon Mamatqulovich KALLA SUYAGI DEFEKTLARINI KRANIOPLASTIKA QILISHNING TARIXIY RIVOJLANISHI BOSQICHLARI.....	17
4. Назарова Жанна Авзаровна, Аббосова Исмигул Алишер кизи ОСОБЕННОСТИ НАРУШЕНИЙ НЕЙРОВЕГЕТАТИВНОЙ РЕГУЛЯЦИИ У ПОЖИЛЫХ ПАЦИЕНТОВ.....	26
5. Abdullayeva Muborak Bekkulovna, Yadgarova Lola Baxadirovna, Aktamova Madinabonu Uktam kizi TOPICAL DIAGNOSTICS, CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF TRIGEMINAL PAIN.....	32
6. Гайбиев Акмал Ахматжонович, Файзимуродов Фахриддин Толипович, Вязикова Наталья Федоровна ЭТИО-ПАТОГЕНЕЗ ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ВРОЖДЕННЫХ СПИНОМОЗГОВЫХ ГРЫЖ В СОЧЕТАНИИ С ПОРОКАМИ ГОЛОВНОГО МОЗГА.....	38
7. Davranov Ismoil Ibragimovich, Xamroqulov Jamshid Dilshod o'g'li BEL OG'RIG'I BO'LGAN BEMORLARNING PATOLOGIK SHAROITLARIDA NEVROLOGIK DIAGNOSTIKANING RADIATION DIAGNOSTIKASI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	44
8. Назарова Жанна Авзаровна, Мамадинова Лола Хамидовна ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЭЛЕКТРОНЕЙРОМИОГРАФИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С САХАРНЫМ ДИАБЕТОМ 2 ТИПА В ЗАВИСИМОСТИ ОТ ИНДЕКСА МАССЫ ТЕЛА.....	50
9. Ходжиева Дилбар Тажиевна, Джаббарова Насиба Юсуповна МИАСТЕНИЯНИНГ КЛИНИК-НЕВРОЛОГИК, НЕЙРОФИЗИОЛОГИК ВА НЕЙНОВИЗУАЛ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.....	54
10. Alixanov Sardorbek Abduvohobovich, Raimova Malika Muxamedjanovna PARKINSON KASALLIGI BO'LGAN BEMORLARNI REABILITATSIYA QILISHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI.....	58
11. Расулова Муниса Бахтияр кизи, Расулова Дилбар Камолиддиновна, Муратов Фахмитдин Хайритдинович ИНСУЛТДАН КЕЙИНГИ АФАЗИЯЛАРНИ ЭРТА РЕАБИЛИТАЦИЯ ҚИЛИШ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.....	62
12. Расулова Дилбар Камалиддиновна КОМОРБИД КАСАЛЛИКЛАР ИНСУЛТ ЯКУНИНИ БАШОРАТЛАШДА ПРЕДИКТОР СИФАТИДА.....	65
13. Усманова Гулчехра Эркиновна СРАВНИТЕЛЬНАЯ ОЦЕНКА ШКАЛ ПРИ ГЕМОМРАГИЧЕСКИХ ИНСУЛЬТАХ.....	70
14. Турсунов Бобирбек Гофуржон ўғли БОЛАЛАРДА ФЕБРИЛ ШАЙТОНЛАШ ХУРУЖЛАРИ ЭТИОЛОГИЯСИ, КЛИНИКАСИ ВА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ДАВОЛАШ УСУЛЛАРИ (АДАБИЁТ ТАХЛИЛИ).....	75
15. Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich CLINICAL AND PSYCHOPATHOLOGIC DYNAMICS OF ANXIETY-DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS IN ADOLESCENTS.....	78
16. Миррахимов Жамшид Абдуллаевич, Эргашева Наргиза Обиджоновна ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИДА ХАЛҚ ТАБОБАТИ УСЛУБЛАРИНИ ЖАМИЯТ САЛОМАТЛИГИНИ САҚЛАШДАГИ РОЛИ ВА МАВЖУД МУАММОЛАР (МАХСУС СЎРОВНОМА АСОСИДА).....	81
17. Миррахимов Жамшид Абдуллаевич, Эргашева Наргиза Обиджоновна, Ахмедова Дилафруз Бахадировна ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ РАСПРОСТРАНЕННОСТИ НЕИНФЕКЦИОННЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ И ПРОГНОЗ ЛЕТАЛЬНЫХ ИСХОДОВ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН.....	88
18. Asadullaev M.M., Mirakhmedova Kh.T., Vakhabova N.M., Jumanazarov D.R., Sohbnazarov N.G., Srojedinov S.Sh., Kalash Dwivedi ETIOLOGICAL STRUCTURE AND COMORBIDITY IN ACUTE ISCHEMIC STROKE.....	93
19. Джуррабекова Азиза Тахировна, Эшимова Шохсанам Кенжабоевна ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНОГО ВЕНОЗНОГО КРОВОТОКА У БОЛЬНЫХ С ДЕГЕНЕРАТИВНЫМИ ПОВРЕЖДЕНИЯМИ ШЕЙНОГО ОТДЕЛА ПОЗВОНОЧНИКА.....	101
20. Hakimov Sardor Shukurjonovich, Kuranbayeva Satima Razzakovna O'TKIR ISHEMIK INSULT RIVOJLANISHIDA NEYROTRANSMITTERLAR VA NEYROGORMONLAR AHAMIYATI..	106

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CLINICAL AND PSYCHOPATHOLOGIC DYNAMICS OF ANXIETY-DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS IN ADOLESCENTS

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ANNOTATION

Depression is a frequently occurring disorder in children and adolescents. Prolonged physical illness affects 10% to 12% of children and adolescents worldwide. These individuals are at greater risk of developing psychological problems, especially anxiety and depression, sometimes directly related to their illness or medical care (e.g., health-related anxiety). There is limited data on the effectiveness of psychological treatments for anxiety and depression in this population. Therapies developed for children and adolescents without health problems may or may not be appropriate for use by those with chronic physical illnesses.

Keywords: degenerative diseases of the cervical spine, venous hemodynamics, duplex scanning.

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КЛИНИКО-ПСИХОПАТОЛОГИЧЕСКУЮ ДИНАМИКА РАЗВИТИЯ ТРЕВОЖНО-ДЕПРЕССИВНЫХ РАССТРОЙСТВ У ПОДРОСТКОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Депрессия является часто встречающимся заболеванием у детей и подростков. Длительные физические заболевания затрагивают от 10% до 12% детей и подростков во всем мире. Эти люди подвергаются большему риску развития психологических проблем, особенно тревоги и депрессии, иногда напрямую связанных с их болезнью или медицинской помощью (например, тревога, связанная со здоровьем). Имеются ограниченные данные об эффективности психологических методов лечения тревоги и депрессии в этой группе населения. Терапия, разработанная для детей и подростков без проблем со здоровьем, может подходить или не подходить для использования теми, у кого есть хронические физические заболевания.

Ключевые слова: дегенеративные заболевания шейного отдела позвоночника, венозная гемодинамика, дуплексное сканирование.

Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

O'SMIRLARDA DEPRESSIV KASALLIKLAR RIVOJLANISHINING KLINIK VA PSIXOPATOLOGIK DINAMIKASI

ANNOTATSIIYA

Depressiya bolalar va o'smirlarda keng tarqalgan kasallikdir. Uzoq muddatli jismoniy kasalliklar butun dunyo bo'ylab bolalar va o'smirlarning 10% dan 12% gacha ta'sir qiladi. Bu odamlar psixologik muammolarni, ayniqsa tashvish va depressiyani rivojlanish xavfi yuqori, ba'zida ularning kasalligi yoki tibbiy yordami bilan bevosita bog'liq (masalan, sog'liq bilan bog'liq tashvish). Ushbu populyatsiyada tashvish va depressiyani psixologik davolash usullarining samaradorligi to'g'risida cheklangan ma'lumotlar mavjud. Sog'liqni saqlash muammosi bo'lmagan bolalar va o'smirlar uchun mo'ljallangan terapiya surunkali jismoniy kasalliklarga chalinganlar uchun mos yoki mos kelmasligi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: bo'yin umurtqalari, dегенератив kasalliklar, venoz gemodinamika, dуплекс skanerlash.

Introduction. Depression is a common condition in children and adolescents. Appropriate and timely care for these patients is essential in primary care settings. A descriptive review of pediatric depression was conducted based on the AAP-endorsed GLAD-PC guidelines for the management of depression in primary care settings. New research regarding suicidality and social media was also reviewed [1]. There are many tools available to assist primary care in the assessment and management of adolescents and children with depression. Key components include: assessment and diagnosis, initial management (including safety planning), treatment, and ongoing management. Comprehensive interviews with patients individually and with caregivers, along with the use of instruments, are critical to the

assessment process [2]. Initial treatment following confirmation of a diagnosis of depression includes safety planning, psychoeducation, and referral to peer support. Evidence-based treatments for depression in children and adolescents include psychotherapy, antidepressants (SSRIs), and a combination of both. Brief psychosocial interventions (BPSIs) have also been demonstrated to be effective compared to CBT. Ongoing treatment is necessary to achieve or maintain remission.

Depression is common in the pediatric population, and it is critical that primary care provides accessible and timely care to this population and their families. Depression is a chronic and recurrent illness that commonly affects children and adolescents [2]. Globally, depression is the leading cause of disability among adolescents worldwide[3].The

rate of depressive disorders among children and adolescents is estimated to be as high as 10%. This means that in any high school class of 30 students, we would expect to find up to 3 individuals suffering from or struggling with depression at any one time. However, about 50% of children and adolescents with depression remain undiagnosed, and even among those who are diagnosed, only half receive appropriate treatment into adulthood [4].

Depression is a chronic relapsing disorder that results in significant morbidity and mortality in adulthood. Approximately 50% of adults with depression report their first episode of depression during adolescence [7]. A follow-up study in the Acute Treatment Study found that approximately 60% of adolescents experience recurrences of depressive disorders after 5 years. Adolescent girls were also more likely to experience recurrence compared with adolescent boys [5]. Sex-related differences are evident in the prevalence of depression after puberty. The prevalence of depression is similar among boys and girls before puberty. However, after puberty, the prevalence of depression among girls becomes 2-3 times higher compared to boys. Theories that have been advanced to explain this difference include significant differences in psychological factors as well as hormonal changes during puberty between boys and girls [6].

Depression can manifest with a wide range of signs and symptoms that are easily confused with other mental disorders in childhood, such as anxiety disorders and/or emotional problems associated with adolescence. Common manifestations of depression in children and adolescents include: sadness and irritability; tearfulness; decreased interest; decreased enjoyment of most activities; low energy; weight loss or gain; sleep disturbances, including hypersomnia; inattention; somatic complaints (brokenness); ambivalence or difficulty making decisions; worthlessness and hopelessness; and suicidal thoughts or gestures [7].

Purpose of the study. To study the peculiarities of cerebral venous blood flow in patients with degenerative injuries and traumas of the cervical spine.

Materials and methods of the study: 88 patients of young age who were treated in the neurological department of the clinic of Samarkand Medical Institute for the period of 2022- 2024 were studied.

Out of the total 270 examined, 150 belonged to group 1 (pre-psychiatric) and 120 belonged to group 2 (psychiatric service). Adolescents aged 12 to 16 years with mean age of 14.6±0.8 years were selected for the study.

Table 1.

Allocation by place of residence

Paul	Number of inspectors	
	1- group (n 150)	2- группа (n-120)
City	83 (55,33%)	70 (58,33%)
Rural	67 (44,67%)	50 (41,67%)
All	150 (100%)	120 (100%)

Results and their discussion. The assessment and diagnosis of depression in children and adolescents should begin with a comprehensive interview. In primary care settings, where scheduled appointments may be short, this interview can be conducted over several visits. However, a risk assessment and safety plan should be completed at the end of the first visit. Clinical assessment of depression should include a discussion with the patient alone and with parents/caregivers. Other sources that can provide important clinical information include teachers, extended family, community agencies (e.g., child welfare services), and any current or former health care providers. During the interview, it is important to establish rapport with the patient and discuss the limits of confidentiality. Clinicians can help establish rapport and engagement by developing a communication plan. This plan may include how information will be shared with caregivers and what information the clinician is required to disclose, what may be useful to disclose with the patient's permission, and what may remain confidential. Several guides are available for physicians who need guidance on how to obtain consent and establish rapport with patients. One useful starting point for discussing confidentiality is to assure patients that information will not be shared between the physician and caregivers without the patient's knowledge and consent. In general, physicians should endeavor to share information with caregivers in the presence of the patient. The limits of confidentiality should also be clear, including in the event of harm to self or others. DSM-5 criteria for major depressive disorder (MDD) require five or more symptoms within a 2-week period and represent a change from previous functioning. At least one of the symptoms must be depressed mood or anhedonia (10). The patient should experience sadness most of the day, almost every day. Irritable mood is also common in the pediatric population with depression. Other diagnostic criteria for evaluation include weight and appetite changes, sleep disturbances, feelings of restlessness or lethargy, and decreased energy. Patients may also struggle with feelings of worthlessness and guilt. Concentration and motivation may also be significantly impaired. In addition to assessing symptoms of depression using DSM 5 criteria, the assessment should also include an evaluation of the patient's functioning at home, school, and with peers, as well as his or her risk for self-harm and suicide (see sidebar). Stressors such as persistent difficulties in school, trauma including emotional, physical, and sexual abuse, as well as bullying, family conflict, and other stressful

life events can also trigger and perpetuate symptoms of depression and poor functioning. Assessment should also include the use of tools, including screening tools and rating scales. Depression screening tools, such as the Modified Patient Health Questionnaire-Modified (PHQ-M) or the Kutcher Adolescent Depression Scale (KADS), can assist clinicians in identifying patients with depression. They are particularly useful in screening children and adolescents, who are less verbally frank about being able to share their symptoms in other ways. General symptom or psychosocial screening such as the Pediatric Symptom Checklist (PSC) may also be used when comorbidities are suspected. The use of rating scales to assess the severity of symptoms of depression can aid in treatment planning. However, no tool can replace a comprehensive and thoughtful clinical interview, although they can play an important additional role in assessment. Many instruments are now available and have been validated in a variety of languages. A validated tool should be used not only during the initial assessment period but also regularly throughout treatment to facilitate monitoring of symptoms of depression. Examples of such tools are available to us free of charge in the GLAD PC toolkit (www.GLADPC.org) and include the PHQ-M mentioned above. As part of the assessment of depression, primary care should also assess concomitant diseases of both a physical and mental nature. The possible influence of comorbidities (e.g., anemia, hypothyroidism) on general symptoms of depression, such as fatigue and sleep disturbances, should be considered. Associated psychiatric disorders, such as anxiety, can significantly affect the presentation of symptoms of depression as well as response to treatment. Other common comorbidities to screen for include substance abuse, learning disabilities, and behavioral disorders. Finally, a small proportion of depressed adolescents will later develop mania and be diagnosed with bipolar disorder.

Conclusions: Thus, assessing a patient's family history for bipolar disorder as well as the patient's own history of episodes of elevated mood (which may include irritability, moodiness, decreased need for sleep, and inattention) is critical before initiating treatment for depression. In particular, treatment of such patients with antidepressants may be ineffective, destabilizing, and may provoke hypomanic or manic episodes. Tools are available for clinicians who want to assess the risk of developing bipolar disorder

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ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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